

THE MAIN FEATURES OF STUDING THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN TWO OR MORE LANGUAGES INCOMPARATIVE LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. *This article due to an assumption important to the comparative method is principle that the laws governing sound change are regular and have no exceptions that cannot be accounted for by some other regular phenomenon of language.*

Keywords: *comparative linguistics, comparative grammar, method, relation words, origin of word.*

Today, the English language has become the most important and clear means of global communication, it does not allow us to be separated from the world and opens the way for rapid development in all aspects of life. It is the most widely used language for cultural and intellectual exchange between different nations and people around the world. In addition, the use of the English language is now necessary not only at the local, but also at the global level of education.

The development of technologies for teaching foreign languages is an important issue. Information civilization requires new standards, and of course any new knowledge quickly becomes obsolete. In general, language innovation means the teacher's creativity and innovation, which changes teaching methods and technology. Educational institutions around the world are introducing innovations based on new ideas, methods and technologies to improve the knowledge of English language teachers [1].

First of all, we need to talk about what pedagogical technology is and how it differs from traditional educational methods. A systematic approach to education is considered the main distinguishing feature of teaching based on pedagogical technology from other approaches. Designing educational goals, content, teaching and learning methods, monitoring and evaluation results in interaction and interdependence are aspects that are often lacking in the traditional educational process. For example, in many cases, education is mainly focused on memorizing information, and the future activity of learners depends on performing certain tasks or making organizational, managerial and professional decisions. Basically, pedagogical technology is a new, unique (innovation) approach to education. It is considered to be a specific expression of the idea of technological organization of education in pedagogy, an image of technocratic consciousness transferred to the field of pedagogy, a certain standardization of the educational process.

First of all, let's talk about the concept of "technology". According to the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, "Technology" is composed of two Greek words: "tekhnos" (techne) - skill, art, understanding, learning, "logos" - science, teaching. found The concept of technology is connected with the content of technological operations and product preparation in the production process. The term technology includes the accumulation of knowledge about the methods and means of implementing processes, as well as the qualitative changes that occur in the object.

Pedagogical technology is understood as an educational process that is guaranteed to achieve educational goals that are similar to technological approaches. Such education is technologically calculated. Technological education is an educational process that does not depend on the personality of the teacher, but is based only on the personal needs, requirements and characteristics of the learner. The learner is at the center of the educational process, and the teacher performs only executive duties.

Pedagogical technology was used as "educational technology" in the USA in the 30s of the 20th century because it was a social necessity, and it meant the use of audio-visual equipment in the educational process.

In this case, the concept of "educational technology" in English means "an educational technology" - a science that provides information on the organization of educational (teaching) processes at the level of high control, art.

Due to the development of science and technology and the educational system, the concept of educational technology has improved and deepened in content. The gradual change of the content of the concept of pedagogical technology includes approximately four periods.

According to J. Winterton, D. Delamare-Le, in the first period (early and mid-50s) in educational institutions, the technical means of information presentation - sound recording and playback means, in other words, the emergence of audiovisual means. It is characterized as follows[2].

The second period (mid-50s-60s) is characterized by the application of the technological approach to the teaching process. The theoretical basis of this approach is the idea of the program. Its technological basis is organized by audio-visual means for educational purposes (feedback devices, electronic classrooms, teaching machines, speech rooms, simulators, etc.).

The third period (70-80s) relied on the achievements of informatics, telecommunication theory, pedagogical quality, systematic analysis and pedagogical sciences in creating the foundations of pedagogical technology. The methodological basis of pedagogical technology has changed, from oral teaching to audio-visual teaching. It is characterized by the creation of computer laboratories, the increase in the number and quality of pedagogical software, and the use of interactive video systems.

Four of the recognition of pedagogical technologies today the period continues. Pedagogical technologies are recognized as interdisciplinary.

He works on the basis of all known branches of pedagogical knowledge and uses the achievements of other disciplines to enrich his scientific concepts.

In conclusion, the concept of pedagogical technology can be interpreted in two ways - firstly, it means the expansion of the use of technical tools in the educational process, and it can be called technology in education, secondly, this concept is educational we can say that the process itself is part of the construction technology.

There are various definitions explaining the essence of the concept of pedagogical technologies, some of them are given below.

According to B. Abdullaeva, pedagogical technology is a set of psychological procedures that determine the composition, i.e., the location of a special set of teaching, educational forms, methods, and educational tools.

Pedagogical technology is the systematization of all personal and methodological tools used to achieve pedagogic goals and their implementation procedure, T. Sattarov, on the other

hand, pedagogic technology comes from the needs of the society and looks at the educational process as an effective shaper of predetermined social qualities of the individual and as a system for its organizers, i.e. the teacher (pedagogue). They believe that it is a technological educational event that evaluates the effects and educational results of students in a certain sequence with the help of educational tools.

In general, today there are various definitions of pedagogical technologies as above, and it is possible to approach it from socio-economic, pedagogical, psychological, didactic, organizational and other points of view.

Modern pedagogical technologies and innovations do not automatically enter the educational system. This process depends on the teacher's activity and motivation. Academician A. Leontiev states that the first condition for understanding the world is activity, and the second condition is education. It is emphasized that people's abilities, knowledge and skills are formed in the process of activity, therefore, activity is a social event and the basic condition of life struggle. That is, activity is a social event, and it is considered an action directed towards goals that meet personal, group, national or universal needs.

Human activity differs from one another according to the goals set before it. For example, creative activity, scientific activity, pedagogical activity, entrepreneurial activity, educational activity, managerial activity and innovative activity.

Today, the old traditional classes do not satisfy the knowledge needs of the listeners, they do not want to listen to such classes. Because thinking and thinking are different, having knowledge of a certain science is different. Thinking and thinking is a product of natural intelligence, and learning is a product of educational institution, pedagogue's activity.

In scientific researches on pedagogy, special attention is paid to the development of the system of forms, methods and tools aimed at eliminating the disparity in the teaching of academic subjects, and the methodology of the teaching and upbringing process, which is their basis.

In particular, in improving the lexical competence of pedagogues, the use of technologies in the modern educational process helps students in the field of foreign languages to correctly form practical lessons from the point of view of methodology and to achieve high results in the field of education. Also, the use of technologies in the educational process helps to make education more attractive and effective.

Pedagogical technologies play an important role in the process of improving staff qualifications. However, it is possible to distinguish teaching method (methodology) from pedagogical technology. Pedagogical technology is the content of the process of pedagogical activity organized on the basis of a specific project, directed to a specific goal and guaranteeing the achievement of this goal. As can be seen from the information given above, the educational methods are focused on the teaching of certain academic subjects and the application of the laws of educational work. Only on the basis of pedagogical technologies that meet the requirements of the time, we can increase the efficiency of the pedagogic personnel who think modernly and master foreign languages. Currently, the development and improvement of pedagogic and production technologies is carried out directly on the basis of information technologies.

When talking about pedagogical technology, it is a set of scientifically based processes of human education and training, which are carried out depending on human thinking, that is, on the intellectual competence of the teacher and the learner. Pedagogical technology is constantly changing

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